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Assessment of Advanced Aerospace Bearing Steel RCF Performances Using a Discriminating Multi-Contact Test

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Abstract:	<p>The "Flat-Washer" or "Unisteel" testing is a well-known technique applied to the basic selection of aircraft bearing materials and their heat treatment prior to, or as an alternative to, full-scale testing. Over the last decade, the continuous decrease of the development cycle time has constrained the aerospace bearing industry to revise its testing means. The interest of a simple, rapid and reproducible test to assess the material performances is then appeared crucial and many testing developments has been made in this way.</p> <p>A history of this elemental screening method is presented to highlight its virtues and its shortcomings. The conclusions of these past developments have been used to design an enhanced version of this material experiment called the Multi-Contact Testing (MCT). A performance comparison is made with previously presented devices to bring out the discriminating power of the MCT concept and its capacity to obtain a statistically significant quantity of data relatively quickly and economically.</p> <p>A typical study is described in this paper to illustrate the performances of the MCT. The study shows the influence of the hardness change of a powder-metallurgy steel on the rolling contact fatigue life.</p>

Assessment of Advanced Aerospace Bearing Steel

RCF Performances Using a Discriminating Multi-Contact Test

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ABSTRACT

The “Flat-Washer” or “Unisteel” testing is a well-known technique applied to the basic selection of aircraft bearing materials and their heat treatment prior to, or as an alternative to, full-scale testing. Over the last decade, the continuous decrease of the development cycle time has constrained the aerospace bearing industry to revise its testing means. A simple, rapid and reproducible test to assess the material performances is then crucial and many testing developments have been made.

A history of this elemental screening method is presented to highlight its virtues and its shortcomings. The conclusions of these past developments have been used to design an enhanced version of this material test method called the Multi-Contact Test (MCT). A performance comparison is made with previously presented devices to bring out the discriminating power of the MCT concept and its capacity to obtain a statistically significant quantity of data relatively quickly and economically.

A typical study is described in this paper to illustrate the performance of the MCT. The study shows the influence of the hardness change of a powder-metallurgy steel on the rolling contact fatigue life.

Keywords

Rolling contact fatigue, Powder-metallurgy HIP steels.

Introduction

The rolling contact fatigue testing of steels and heat treatments and in particular bearing life testing, can be an expensive undertaking both in time, equipment investment, consumables and energy. It is tempting to try to use substitute specimen/bench type tests and in the past, when the steel quality (compared to today requirements) was relatively poor, useful metallurgical correlations could be obtained by standard flat washer testing.

Rolling bearings in service are expected to tolerate contact fatigue damage under multi contact conditions. Giga cycle ultrasonic push-pull fatigue testing [1] is an efficient way to accumulate ultra-high cycle fatigue data. The volume of material stressed in the selected test is a significant consideration and the use of non-contact push-pull or rotating bend fatigue testing is advocated to correlate bearing steel technologies with fatigue properties [2, 3].

A significant amount of literature exists on contact fatigue testing and an ASTM symposium was held on the subject in 1981 [4] and with reference to the ASTM symposium held in 1946 [5] the industry has been engaged for a long time with the same predicament of testing capabilities and testing costs. Flat washer testing is an established rolling contact fatigue test because the relatively simple flat washer test element is attractive. However, is this standard test capable of discriminating the multi contact (high cycle) fatigue properties of modern bearing steel

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3 technologies?
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6 **REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES USING FLAT TESTING AND CORRELATIONS**
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8 **WITH METALLURGICAL PARAMETERS IN ROLLING BEARING STEELS:**
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10 The ASTM STP's are a useful source of information on rolling contact fatigue testing
11 technologies and the ASTM STP flat washer testing literature is summarized as follows:
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14 - The Sanyo Special Steel paper from 1975 described flat washer contact fatigue testing
15 and the effect of nonmetallic inclusions on fatigue life in air melt and re-melt bearing steel
16 grades [6].
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19 - Flat washer testing was applied in the RHP, UK 1982 paper to demonstrate both heat
20 treatment, steel process and quality relationships in bearing steels [7].
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23 - A Rolls-Royce UK paper described a modified flat washer (Unisteel) test on aircraft
24 engine bearing steels running with synthetic lubrication [8]. At the time it was said that the high
25 load synthetic lubricant flat washer testing bridged a gap between basic metallography
26 examination of bearing steels and full-scale rig testing or engine testing.
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28
29 - Several year's experience of "element" and full-bearing materials testing is described in
30 an SKF Group 1982 paper [9]. One of the conclusions from the paper was that the selected
31 element test (such as flat washer) must reflect the failure mode observed in rolling bearing
32 applications. This is a legitimate conclusion particularly in view of the current change from
33 subsurface inclusion/steel cleanliness spalling to the surface distress bearing raceway failure
34 modes.
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37 - A Sanyo Special Steel follow-up paper described the effect of contact fatigue subsurface
38 microstructure transformations (plate like carbides) in ball thrust washer rolling contact fatigue
39 testing [10]. The atypical material flow in the flat washers test elements is highlighted in this
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3 paper.

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5 - In a follow-up to the 1982 paper RHP UK concluded from flat washer testing that
6 titanium carbonitrides were benign with respect to rolling contact fatigue strength [11]. At the
7 time the benign nature of the titanium carbonitrides was a significant observation as the bearing
8 industry was in the process of tightening the titanium specification for 1C-1.5Cr steels based on
9 rotating beam fatigue tests.

10
11 - In a 1993 publication the French bearing steel producer (Ascometal) used flat washer
12 testing to vindicate the use of rotary continuously cast steel for the production of tubes for
13 bearing ring applications [12].

14
15 - A defined flat washer testing methodology (FB2) is described in an SNR paper from
16 2002 [13]. The FB2 testing is an established material quality test still in use today.

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18 - In a 2007 publication FB2 test results, for low reduction ratio steels, were correlated with
19 inclusion populations using extreme value statistical test methods [14].

20
21 - In an Ascometal/FAG publication the FB2 flat washer test was shown to discriminate the
22 effect of heat treatment/microstructure (effect of cleanliness and fatigue strength) whereas a full
23 bearing test did not (showed the response of debris denting accommodation) [15].

24
25 - In 2010, Sanyo Special Steel published the results of flat washer testing in which the
26 effects of inclusion/matrix interfaces cavities could be resolved [16]. A “remarkable
27 improvement” in rolling contact fatigue life was reported by closing the inclusion/matrix
28 interface by the application of hot isostatic pressing (HIP).

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30 - The UK bearing steel industry experience of flat washer (Unisteel) rolling contact fatigue
31 testing was published in 2012 [17]. The conclusion was that when the 1-1.5Cr steel oxygen level
32 was typically below 8 ppm it took several weeks to generate meaningful test data for a single
33

heat of steel and alternative testing methodologies were required.

- A very detailed analysis of the flat washer FB2 test was reported in 2015 [18] by Ascometal. A unique feature of the flat washer test element is that the spalled ring may be fractured to reveal the metallurgical defect responsible for the subsurface initiated rolling contact fatigue spalling. From the publication, 86% of the 52100 steel test rings had subsurface fatigue zones and 53% of the fatigue zones contain stringer inclusion.

Information on the element/specimen type material test machines is summarized in table 1.

Year		Equipment Description:	Ball Size (mm):	Speed (rpm):	Contact Pressure (GPa):	Comments:
1950	NASA	5-ball spin rig				
	DUCOM	TR 30L 4-ball	12.7	10000		Used for lubricant/additive testing
1982	Unisteel (Mayes)	Flat washer testing				Steel quality levels (oxygen)
	Derivative of Unisteel, FB2 (NTN-SNR)	Flat Washer derivative testing (15 balls, 2 washers) 675 000 rep./hr.	9.922	1500	4.2	Test rings easily fractured for analysis (stress conc.), full lubrication EHD or lower λ
	MORI Thrust type test (Sanyo Special Steel) Japan	Flat washer RCF (3 balls)	9,525	1800	5.26	With or without contaminant additions.
	Polymet profiled roller -- > test rod	Test rod	-			
	3-ball on rod, NTN Federal Mogul (supplied by Delta Res. Livonia)	3-ball on rod (rod dia. 9,5mm)	12.7			Avoid problem of material flow none conformance. Steels balls can be replaced by ceramic balls.
	Japanese Mori ball-on-rod machine	3-ball on rod (rod dia. 12 mm)	19.05 (3/4 inch)	46240		
	1 point RCF test	Sample shaft (test shaft dia. 17mm)- ceramic balls	9.525 (3/8 inch)			Study of crack initiation and propagation.

	Two-disc machine (commercial Plint TE74)	20 mm OD & a 100 mm OD	X			High vol. at risk (rolling & sliding speeds and T controlled), not pure subsurface initiation. Failure (contamination or artificial defect need to be introduced), vibration sensor for spalling detection
1970	Contra-Rotating ring rig (Rolls-Royce)	Contra-rotating shafts		10000		Thrust washer temp. up to 180°C
	Plint TE 92HS RCF Thrust Washer Test	4-ball test configuration TE92/3				TE92/3 with microscope for wear scar examination // with cone configuration

Table 1. Summary of Element/Specimen Material Tests.

The flat washer is attractive as a test element due to its simplicity/low cost and it may be concluded from the available information that the standard flat washer test can provide information about the steel subsurface initiated rolling contact fatigue strength. An attractive feature of flat washer testing is the post-test diagnostics capability; ring spitting giving information about the failure initiator. However, are the standard test conditions representative of the long life, multi contact loading conditions?

DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR AN IMPROVED WASHER TESTING METHODOLOGY:

The following design parameters were considered for an improved flat washer testing methodology:

- Simple flat washer with reasonable test size, reasonable dimensional and surface finish tolerances,
- Robust machine with load calibration capability and reproducible alignment,
- Test loads high enough to produce spalling failure without macro plasticity and raceway grooving,

- Zero ball failures/damage,
- Multi contact loading by use of small balls and a doubling of the rotation speed (compared to standard flat washer tests),
- Early spalling detection and machine cutoff.

The test parameters for the SKF Aerospace multi contact test are summarized in Table 2.

Equipment Description:	Ball Size (mm):	Speed (rpm):	Contact Pressure (GPa):	Comments:
Flat Washer derivative testing (27 balls, 2 washers) 2655 036 rep./hr.	5.556 (7/32 inch)	3000	1.5-7 GPa	Full lubrication EHD (or lower λ); Variable contact pressure.

Table 2. Summary of SKF Aerospace Multi Contact Test.

TEST MACHINE CONFIGURATION:

A global overview of the test benches is given in Figure 1. A set of five independent test benches is available. It allows easy individual maintenance of the test rigs.

A schematic of the test rig is presented in Figure 2. The load is applied vertically. The shaft drives the double-grooved washer. Two samples are tested in the test rig (Figure 2), so two samples surfaces are tested at the same time. The motor speed (as shown in Table 2) is 3000 rpm.

The test runs in full film lubricated (elasto-hydrodynamic regime) in standard conditions.

Figure 1. Global overview of the MCT test benches.

TEST ELEMENT SPECIFICATION:

Possible operating conditions:

- The pitch diameter on the surface washer is 60 mm.
- 2 flat washers (tested samples) per rig.
- 27 or 9 balls per surface test sample. Ceramic Si_3N_4 balls: dia. 5.556 mm or 7.144 mm.
- Rotational Speed: 3000 rpm.
- Full lubrication EHD.
- PEEK cage, PTFE cage, copper alloys cage.
- Contact pressure: 1.5-7 GPa.
- Oil lubrication Mil L 23699 at 40 °C.
- Oil Temperature & Vibration monitoring.

For a testing configuration with diameter balls of 5.556mm, the test is driven with 27 balls and corresponds to about 2.8×10^6 stress repetitions per hour.

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3 Spalling is detected by accelerometer. Fatigue lifetime of tested material is calculated by
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5 statistical Weibull analysis. The concept of test benches which is modular (in terms of ball size,
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7 instrumentation, surface defects such as scratches, large range of applied pressure ...) allows
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9 various open testing strategies. While using nominal conditions (nominal suspension time of 500
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11 hours), one material campaign is run in about two months.
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Figure 2. Description of Multi Contact Test Configuration (Schematic of test rig).

MATERIALS SCREENING with MCT (elementary RCF)

Two batches of Flat Washers from Powder metallurgy route have been proposed for Rolling Contact Fatigue testing. Both batches have been made from a High Speed Steel grade supersaturated in carbon and with a high cobalt content (~10.5% in weight). The nominal composition is shown in Table 3.

	PM High Speed Steel
C	2.25 – 2.35
Mn	0.10 – 0.50
Si	0.40 – 0.80
Cr	3.75 – 4.50
Mo	6.50 – 7.50
V	6.25 – 6.75
Co	10.0 – 11.0
W	6.0 – 7.0

Table 3. Nominal composition of PM High Speed Steel (AMS 6560).

This is a promising grade for a high load capability bearing reaching high hardness and fine microstructure with well dispersed carbides.

The two batches of Flat Washers (Table 4) have been produced using the same process of Powder metallurgy consisting of gas atomization of powder, powder compaction in capsule (“green shape”) followed by HIPing (Hot Isostatic Processing) at high temperature. The capsule is hot-worked into bar and soft annealed. The manufacturing sequences are summarized in the table 4. The only change in process in between both tested batches is the applied heat treatment (chosen for reaching specific target hardness): the first batch is intended to get hardness close to conventional M50 steel (~ 63 HRC) and the second batch a very high hardness close to 69 HRC. The heat treatments information will be detailed in the next section.

Grade and Process	Manufacturing Process operations			
	PM-HIP AMS 6560	HIP-ed bar	Rough machining	HT (hardening + tempering)

Table 4. Manufacturing process of PM-HIP AMS 6560 Flat Washers.

* Samples roughness of Flat Washers:

The surface roughness obtained corresponds to the finish grinding operation applied. The roughness values are (with a gaussian filter $\lambda_c=0.25\text{mm}$) at an average Ra value equal to $0.05\ \mu\text{m}$

(+/-0.01). The Rz parameter value is about 0.42 μm (+/-0.1 μm).

MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION

The composition of this PM High Speed Steel (conform with AMS 6560) is designed as a secondary hardening steel. The heat treatment and secondary hardening information are given in the ASP 2060 data sheet [19]. As with all HSS's the achievable hardness's are a function of the austenitization and secondary hardening tempering parameters, but for bearings steels the heat treatment parameters must be selected to have as near as possible zero retained austenite, avoiding a significant sacrifice in toughness.

Austenitization - Quenching	Temper	Hardness (at 20°C)
@975°C	3x 1h @560°C	63.7-64 HRC (HV50)
@1150°C	3x 1h @560°C	68.6 HRC

Table 5. Heat treatments and Hardnesses of PM-HIP AMS 6560 Flat Washers.

The austenitizing temperature (shown in Table 5) is higher for the last treatment, this results in better homogenization and after quenching in a higher matrix hardness close to 69 HRC. The secondary hardening is equivalent (Table 5).

The microstructures resulting from the applied heat treatments are shown in Figure 3. Two main types of carbides are present in HSS: MC-carbides (generally noticed as VC) and M_6C [20]. On PM M50 HSS (according to [21]), they have been identified under SEM-BSE: the MC type are darker compared to the M_6C -type. Powder metallurgy process is interesting with inert gas atomization because it can lead to fine microstructure. For both hardened samples as observed in micrographs in Figure 3, the microstructures are fine: the carbides are well dispersed with a size

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3 mostly inferior to 3 μm . In comparison, the VIM + VAR M50 steel leads to bigger primary
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carbides of sizes in the range 5-10 μm and arranged into cluster [22].

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of microstructure after chemical etching (Vilella's reagent) for PM-HIP AMS 6560 samples (at x1000): a) 63-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

Figure 4. SEM image showing carbides on PM-HIP: a) 63-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

The presence of alloying elements in carbides has been determined by EDS mapping (not shown here): the darker carbides (shown in Figure 4) contain chromium, molybdenum, vanadium and tungsten while the brighter ones (in Figure 4) contain at least tungsten and molybdenum.

The morphology of carbides can be reported: for both hardened samples (Figure 4 a) and b)), the carbides are rounded with a uniform dispersion (a bit less round for 69 HRC sample). As a first evaluation of the carbide sizes, the carbide horizontal length has been measured on SEM images for both samples (as shown in Figure 5 a) and b)). The carbides on the 64 HRC sample seem a little bit smaller than those on the maximum hardened material. Moreover, smaller carbides with sizes from 0.16-0.25 μm (that could be of same nature as the previous brighter ones) are present on 64 HRC sample, as shown in Figure 5 a).

These smaller carbides have not been found on the 69 HRC sample, so it is thought that they

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have been dissolved during austenitization at a higher temperature. They are not expected to be tempering carbides as the tempering treatment applied was the same. In addition, in literature tempering carbides were found to be different in quenched and tempered M50 HSS than those found here (different in morphology: one population elongated (0.05-0.5 μm in length, M_3C type) and one population of carbide precipitates 5-15nm in length [22]).

Figure 5. SEM image (at magnification x10 000) showing carbides lengths on PM-HIP samples: a) 63,7-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

A 2D image analysis has been performed on microstructure images in order to quantify the average carbide size and the carbide fraction. The images representative of the microstructure (with chosen appropriate magnification of 5000 times – as shown in Figure 4) have been used for this purpose. Two images per sample (corresponding to a total area of $1081 \mu\text{m}^2$ per sample) have been analyzed for the evaluations of carbide size distribution and carbide area fraction.

The image treatment using ImageJ can be described into 3 steps: optimization of brightness/contrast, binarization, threshold area $0,012 \mu\text{m}^2$ to count particles (corresponding to the minimum diameter of particle considered $0,12 \mu\text{m}$). Images after binarization and for particle counts are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Post-treated images for the 68.6HRC sample:
a) after binarization and b) after particle counts.

The results of the image analysis are plotted in Figure 7.

- For 68.6 HRC sample, there is only one carbide population in size from 0.5 to 3 μm (134 particles in this range size). It seems clear that - for the 68.6 HRC sample - particles with sizes under 0.5 μm (ie. 88 particles in Figure 7b)) should not be considered in the analysis; because irregularities of this size range remained after post-treatment in Figure 6 in comparison to the real microstructure in Figure 5b). These irregularities represent 13% of the “carbide” area but only 3,1% of the analyzed area, so it will not alter the fraction evaluation. The average carbide diameter (considering [0.5-3[μm range) is 1,35 μm for 68.6 HRC sample (table 6). The maximum diameter that have to be considered is 3 μm (because the higher diameters obtained in the analysis seem to come from particles that have coalesced).

- On the 64 HRC sample, the amount of carbides in the range [0,5-3[μm is 145 particles, which represents roughly the same population quantity. The average diameter size of this population is

1,32 μm . Moreover, the smaller carbides population (with sizes $\leq 0.25 \mu\text{m}$) represents a small percentage of the total carbides area (2.7%). The average diameter of this population is $\sim 0,20 \mu\text{m}$. For information, the average carbide diameter for 64 HRC sample in the overall size range ([0,16-3]) is $0,6 \mu\text{m}$.

Finally, it should be noted that the carbide area fractions for both AMS 6560 steel samples are almost identical with fraction values of 23,4 and 23,8 % (respectively for 64 HRC and 68.6 HRC samples).

Figure 7. Carbide diameter distribution (particle counts vs. upper class limit) on PM-HIP samples hardened at: a) 63,7-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

Carbide size analysis	Diameter size populations (μm)	Particle counts	Average size / population (μm)	Area % of the carbide population	Total particle counts		Carbide Area fraction (%)
63.7-64 HRC	[0,16-0,25]	211	0,20	2,5 % (area= $6,7\mu\text{m}^2$) => 2,7%	([0,16-3[range) 322	467	X
	[0,5-3[145	1,32	89 % (area= $235,5\mu\text{m}^2$) => 97,3%	145		22,4 (23,4 for overall range [0,5-4])
68.6 HRC	[0,5-3[134	1,35	87 % (area = $229\mu\text{m}^2$)	224		21,2 (23,8 for overall range [0,5-6])

Table 6. Carbide size and fraction results from image microstructure analysis for both AMS 6560 PM-HIP hardened Flat Washers.

Even if the size distributions are different (due to different austenitization temperatures), the carbide fractions are still identical for both AMS 6560 hardened Flat Washers. This is a high level of carbide fraction reached by this material from Powder metallurgy giving good resistance to abrasive wear (in the case of poor lubrication conditions). This is 5 times a higher carbide fraction value than what is obtained on ingot VIM + VAR M50 steel (4.7% by Rietveld XRD [21] or 4.6% by tomography [23]).

A rough identification after image analysis for the 69 HRC sample gives a ratio of 1/5 for the brighter carbides (distinguished by SEM).

* Rating of non-metallic inclusions has been done by optical microscopy according to ASTM E45 Method A – Worst fields (160mm^2). For indication, the results for 63.7-64 HRC samples are extracted from the bar Conformity certificate. The cleanliness results are presented in Table 7.

Inclusion Type	Micro-inclusion rating			
	A	B	C	D
AMS6560 norm	Thin 1.5	Thin 1.5	Thin 1.5	Thin 1.5
	Heavy 1.0	Heavy 1.0	Heavy 1.0	Heavy 1.0
Bar of PM-HIP 63.7-64 HRC	1.5 thin	1 thin	0	0.5 thin 0.5 heavy

Table 7. Cleanliness results.

Inclusion rating results are expected to be similar for both materials, because they come from the same steel manufacturer and they have been subjected to the same processing.

* Testing conditions:

The Multi-Contact testing conditions for the tested batches are summarized in Table 8. Ceramic balls are used ($E=310$ GPa). The total applied force is high (4200 N), and this corresponds to contact pressures of 4,1 to 4,4 GPa (according to the tested material, Table 9) higher than in current aeroengine applications (1.8-2 GPa). This is aimed to accelerate the test of the material - while not inducing macro-plasticity – and still keeping the discriminating power of the Multi-Contact testing.

Equipment Description:	Ceramic Ball, Size (mm):	Speed (rpm):	Contact Force (N):	Comments:
Flat Washer derivative testing (27 balls, 2 washers) 2655 036 rep./hr.	5.556 (7/32 inch)	3000	4200	Full lubrication EHD (oil temperature 40°C +/-1°C)

Table 8. MCT Testing conditions.

Flat Washer material	M50 HSS	PM-HIP AMS 6560
E (GPa)	204	250
Hertz pressure (MPa)	4112	4442

Depth z_0 (max. shear stress) (mm)	0,065	0,062
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Table 9. Testing conditions (Contact Pressure) of the tested Flat Washer material.

* RCF results analysis and discussion.

The depth of maximum Hertzian contact is very shallow (calculated to be 62-65 μ m) with a Hertz pressure of 4.1-4.44 GPa. This ensures that the maximum contact pressure is applied in the subsurface of through-hardened material (or in the case-hardened layer if needed).

For the baseline M50 HSS and PM-HIP AMS6560 at 69 HRC, about 30 tests per material batch was performed, whereas it was less for AMS 6560 at 64 HRC.

Statistical Weibull analysis for RCF life determination

A dedicated tool is used for the statistical Weibull analysis. Weibull plots are presented in Figure

8. The main results calculated are shown in Table 9 and compared to the VIM + VAR M50 steel.

Figure 8. Weibull probability plot of PM-HIP AMS 6560 hardened materials and baseline M50 steel (MCT results).

The baseline M50 HSS (~63 HRC) has a L10 life of about 474 million of cycles (upper limit in confidence bound is ~500 million of cycles).

	L ₁₀ (M cycles)	L ₅₀ (M cycles)	β (slope)
VIM VAR M50 (~63HRC)	474	1517	2.06
PM-HIP AMS 6560 (63.7-64 HRC)	432	2645	1.36
PM-HIP AMS 6560 (68.6 HRC)	807	2485	2.58

Table 10. RCF life results from Multi-Contact Testing.

As the number of failures is more limited for PM-HIP AMS 6560 at 63.7 HRC, its confidence bound is enlarged compared to the other tested materials. However, it should be noted that the

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3 PM-HIP AMS 6560 (63.7 HRC) confidence bound is overlapping M50 steel and so for L10 life
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5 this material performs potentially as well as M50 steel.
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8 The PM-HIP material hardened at 68.6 HRC shows the highest RCF L10 life of about 800
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10 million cycles (Table 9). This is a very significant improvement (factor 1.7) in RCF life
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12 compared to the M50 steel baseline attributed to the hardness increase (+5.6 HRC). Also, both
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14 PM-HIP materials show an increase in L50 (with a 1.6 factor) over M50 steel (Table 9).
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16 However, to interpret properly this parameter it could be interesting to increase the suspension
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18 time in order to get physically closer to L50 time.
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22 The better the slope value, the better is the RCF reliability. A typical value of around 2 is
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24 obtained for M50 HSS. This slope reveals a reduced distribution in life and so a controlled
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26 process of manufacturing. The slope is even better for PM-HIP AMS6560 hardened at 68.6 HRC
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28 with a value near to 2.6. The tighter carbide distribution (centered at about 1.3 μm) is mostly
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30 explaining this good property.
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34 The lower slope value obtained for PM-HIP hardened at 63.7 HRC (~1.4) could have been
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36 eventually improved while increasing its batch size. Besides, this is showing that a minimum size
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38 of batch is needed which will lead to a minimum number of failures to be plotted (~10 failures
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40 seems appropriate).
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45 **DISCUSSION**

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47 The macroscopic hardness (that can be linked to the yield strength) seems to be of importance for
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49 RCF life. We can clearly see the hardness trend influence on L10 life. As an indication, an
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51 increase of 1 HRC point is related to 12,5% increase of RCF life in MCT configuration.
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55 The RCF life is determined by spalling initiation. When limiting the carbide size (carbides are
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3 seen as stress raisers), the stress in the surrounding matrix is decreased for the same load. So this
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5 will limit debonding and the material will tolerate locally higher stress before initiating crack.
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7 Therefore, the reduction in (maximum) carbide size can be related to the increase of RCF life.
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9 The maximum carbide size observed for this PM-HIP material is only 3 μ m in diameter. The
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11 carbides in this through-hardened PM-HIP steel appear significantly smaller by 2.5 to 5 times
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13 compared to the VIM VAR M50 HSS and this is partly explaining the higher RCF performance
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15 observed (factor 1.7 in MCT for AMS 6560 hardened at 69 HRC compared to M50). Moreover,
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17 as the carbide size distribution is well reduced, the reliability in RCF is also improved compared
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19 to the baseline M50. These interpretations are mainly based on the results of PM-HIP AMS 6560
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21 at 69 HRC as the batch quantity for the same material at 64 HRC was limited.
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27 The residual stresses for this material are only at the surface and it is supposed to be similar for
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29 the three compared materials (grinding effect is generating compressive residual stresses only in
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31 20-30 μ m depth).
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37 The alloy composition is also very different between M50 and PM-HIP AMS6560. The additions
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39 of substantial carbon and alloying elements (Mo +2%, V +5.5%, W6-7%) allow a higher carbide
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41 content (around 23%) which results in better abrasive wear and more stable carbides (example
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43 VC). The cobalt addition is responsible for hot hardness and RCF tests at high temperature
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45 should be done in order to prove its beneficial effect.
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49 The observation of the microstructure damage in the flat washers' sections under the raceway
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51 (not shown here) can bring additional information to understand the RCF life of the bearing
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53 materials.
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CONCLUSIONS

The application of the MCT concept for screening advanced aeroengine bearing grade materials such as PM-HIP AMS 6560 has been done. The following results could be underlined:

- It has been shown that a hardness increase can generate a given increase in RCF life.
- The refinement in carbide size observed on AMS 6560 steel is shown as a direct benefit of PM-HIP process regarding the RCF life.
- The MCT concept allows to generate statistical data quite quickly and economically.
- The discriminating power of Multi-Contact test bench has been highlighted. A minimum batch size (function of the material) has been evidenced for given confidence bounds. A hardness difference of at least 1 HRC between two tested materials seems to be the screening limit in the current testing conditions (with appropriate batch size identified).

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Bathias “Gigacycle fatigue properties of bearing steels”, ASTM STP1524, 2010, p 160-178 Ed. J.M. Beswick
- [2] A.A. Hamedany “Fatigue model of bearing steel based on stressed volume”, Material Science and Technology, 2016, Vol 32 No 5, p 466-479
- [3] K. Ryden and T. B. Lund “Rotating beam testing of bearing steels – An effective rolling contact fatigue test complement”, ASTM STP 1548, 2012, p 203-217 Ed. J.M. Beswick
- [4] Rolling Contact Fatigue Testing of Bearing Steels, ASTM STP771, 1982 Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [5] Symposium on Testing of Bearing, ASTM STP70, 1947 Ed. Admin Committee on Simulated Service Testing
- [6] M. Kinoshi and A. Koyanagi "Effect of nonmetallic inclusions on rolling-contact fatigue life in bearing steels," ASTM STP575, 1975, p 138-149 Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [7] J. M. Hampshire et al "Materials evaluation by flat washer testing" ASTM STP771, 1982 p 46-66 Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [8] K.L. Day "Unisteel testing of aircraft engine bearing steel, ASTM STP771,.1982, p 67-84 Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [9] G.B. Johnston et al "Experience of element and full-bearing testing of materials over several years" ASTM STP771, 1982, p 190-205, Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [10] K. Tsubota and A. Koyanagi "Effect of platelike carbides below the rolling surface in a ball-washer thrust rolling contact fatigue tester" ASTM STP771, 1982, p 380-391, ed. J.J.C. Hoo
- [11] J.M. Hampshire and E. King "Quantitative inclusion ratings and continuous casting: User experience and relationships with rolling contact fatigue life" ASTM STP987, 1988, p 61-80 Ed. J.J.C. Hoo

- 1
2
3 [12] G. Baudry, et al, "Use of rotary continuous cast steel for production of tubes for bearing
4 applications" ASTM STP 1195, 1993, p 293-307, Ed. J.J.C. Hoo
5
6
7
8 [13] D. Girodin et al, "Rolling contact fatigue tests to investigate surface initiated damage and
9 tolerance to surface dents" ASTM STP1419, 2002, p 263-281 Ed. J.M. Beswick
10
11
12 [14] D. Girodin et al, "Statistical analysis of nonmetallic inclusions for the estimation of rolling
13 contact fatigue range and quality control of bearing steel", ASTM STP1465, 2007 p 85-100 Ed.
14 J.M. Beswick
15
16
17
18 [15] P. Daguier et al, "New development in through hardened bearing steel grades for use in
19 contaminated lubrication", ASTM STP1465, 2007 p 131-139 Ed. J.M. Beswick
20
21
22
23 [16] N. Tsunekage et al, "Initiation behavior of crack originated from non-metallic inclusion in
24 rolling contact fatigue", ASTM STP1524, 2010 p 97-109 Ed. J.M. Beswick
25
26
27
28 [17] P. F. Morris and S. Carey "Advanced methods for assessing the quality of bearing steels",
29 ASTM STP1548, 2012 p 268-288 Ed. J.M. Beswick
30
31
32
33 [18] M. Millot-Meheux and E. Henault, "Flat washer test practice-Statistical analysis", ASTM
34 STP 1580 2015 p 538-549
35
36
37
38 [19] Erasteel Data Sheet for ASP 2060,
39
40
41 www.erasteel.com/sites/default/files/media/document/GB_Grade_ASP2060.pdf
42
43 [20] Sundin S, Nordberg L-O, Cocco M an Walve R, "Innovations in high performance gas-
44 atomised PM steels", Proceedings of the 2008 World PM Congress, Session 51-1, Washington,
45 MPIF, 2008.
46
47
48
49 [21] Powder and ingot metallurgical bearing steels, "Comparison in terms of phase
50 transformation and mechanical behavior". G. Guétard, University of Cambridge, PhD Thesis,
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

[22] M.A. Klecka, G. Subhash, N.K. Arakere, “Microstructure-property relationships in M50NiL and P675 case-hardened bearing steels”, Tribology Transactions, 56 (6) (2013) 1046-1059.

[23] “Damage mechanism related to plasticity around heterogeneous inclusions under rolling contact loading in hybrid bearings ceramic/steel”. K. Amuzuga, INSA Lyon, PhD Thesis, 244p., 2016.

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Figure 1. Global overview of the MCT test benches.

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Figure 2. Description of Multi Contact Test Configuration (Schematic of test rig).

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of microstructure after chemical etching (Vilella's reagent) for PM-HIP AMS 6560 samples (at x1000): a) 63-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

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Figure 4. SEM image showing carbides on PM-HIP: a) 63-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

Figure 5. SEM image (at magnification x10 000) showing carbides lengths on PM-HIP samples: a) 63,7-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

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Figure 6. Post-treated images for the 68.6HRC sample:
a) after binarization and b) after particle counts.

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4 a) 64 HRC

Carbide distribution

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22 b) 68.6 HRC

Carbide distribution

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Figure 7. Carbide diameter distribution (particle counts vs. upper class limit) on PM-HIP samples hardened at: a) 63,7-64 HRC, b) 68.6 HRC.

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Figure 8. Weibull probability plot of PM-HIP AMS 6560 hardened materials and baseline M50 steel (MCT results).